

Thermal Evolution of the Lunar Magma Ocean Controlled By Tidal Heating

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The 4.35 Ga Puzzle of the Moon

Using the solidification of the **Lunar Magma Ocean (LMO)** to date the Moon's formation is a long-standing idea. Yet diverse samples — mare-basalt source regions, ferroan anorthosites (FANs), urKREEP and the Mg-suite — converge on **4.35 ± 0.05 Ga**. If the LMO cooled quickly, that age *is* the Moon's age; but other evidence points to an **older Moon** (~4.50 Ga). Reconciling these makes 4.35 Ga a genuine **puzzle**.

Proposed answers each fall short: a **young-Moon** formation (panel B), a **reset** of the ages by a later event (panel C), or **slower LMO cooling** (panel D) — which can delay solidification but struggles to terminate it **rapidly**, as the tight age cluster requires. We argue that all of these overlook one heat source capable of producing exactly this behavior: **tidal heating of the magma ocean itself** (panel A).

Fig. 1. (A) Tidal-heating model: a high-heat plateau holds the LMO molten, then collapses at ~4.35 Ga, pinning all products to one age. (B) Young-Moon (fast cooling), (C) reset and (D) delayed-cooling paradigms. Sample/zircon data after Borg & Carlson (2023).

Self-regulating Longevity & Collapse

In a coupled 0-D thermal-orbital model, tidal dissipation *within* the LMO dominates the lunar energy budget (~30–500 TW, > **an order of magnitude** above radiogenic) for >100 Myr — holding a long-lived high-heat **plateau** that then ends in a rapid **cliff** near 4.35 Ga. This reconciles the >100 Myr delay with the sharp, near-simultaneous solidification recorded by the samples. The energy budget is

$$\dot{E}_{\text{LMO}} = \dot{E}_{\text{tide}} + \dot{E}_{\text{rad}} + \dot{Q}_{\text{CMB}} - \dot{Q}_{\text{conv}}$$

Fig. 3. Heating/cooling terms for the baseline case ($e = 0.05$, $Q_E/k_2 = 400$). Tidal heating \dot{E}_{tide} (orange) self-regulates to balance convective loss $-\dot{Q}_{\text{conv}}$ (black) across the plateau, then **collapses** near 4.35 Ga and drops below radiogenic heating \dot{E}_{rad} (green) within <30 Myr — the **thermal cliff**.

Why so abrupt? With radiogenic heating alone the Moon's thermal evolution is an approximately **linear** system that cools monotonically. **Tidal** heating instead depends on **rheology** (viscosity) — and the viscosity itself depends on temperature and melt fraction, feeding back on the heating. This makes the system strongly **nonlinear**: it **self-sustains** before 4.35 Ga, then **collapses abruptly** at ~4.35 Ga.

Tidal Heating of a “Magma Ocean” Matters

Tidal heating arises from the **continual stretching** of the Moon by Earth's gravity, and its strength is set by two factors: the **forcing** exerted on the Moon and the Moon's own **response** to that forcing.

Both end-members respond weakly: a **fully solid** Moon (near-elastic) and a **fully liquid** magma ocean (low viscosity) dissipate little. In between, a **mushy** state dissipates **orders of magnitude** more — and the crystallizing magma ocean passes *exactly* through this window.

Fig. 2. Cooling power (blue) vs. idealized tidal heating (red) along the crystallization path (green). Heating rises to meet cooling at a **stable equilibrium** (self-regulating plateau, stages 1–2); continued recession lowers the heating branch until balance becomes **unstable** (stage 3), triggering rapid collapse.

Born Asymmetric: The Lunar Dichotomy

Tidal heating is not distributed evenly: the **nearside** is forced more strongly than the **farside**, so the two hemispheres cross the collapse at slightly different times. The Moon may therefore have been **born asymmetric** at ~4.35 Ga.

Fig. 4. (A) Near-/far-side asymmetric solidification at ~4.35 Ga and (B) the resulting post-4.35 Ga cumulate structure (asymmetric crust, urKREEP and Fe-Ti enrichment).

A first-order hemispheric correction predicts a short-lived thermal contrast ($\Delta T \sim 20\text{--}80\text{ K}$ near the cliff) that may **seed the lunar dichotomy**.